

[RESULTS] Applying Transfer Learning to Sentiment Analysis in social media

Summary

Models

- BETO
- BERT Multilingual
- SVC

Validation results

- *#1 Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset*
 - Training dataset: Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset
 - Validation datasets: Emotion Dataset for NLP, SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset, Twitter Reviews Dataset
- *#2 Emotion Dataset for NLP*
 - Training dataset: Emotion Dataset for NLP
 - Validation datasets: Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset, SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset, Twitter Reviews Dataset
- *#3 SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset*
 - Training dataset: SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset
 - Validation datasets: Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset, Emotion Dataset for NLP, Twitter Reviews Dataset
- *#4 Twitter Reviews Dataset*
 - Training dataset: Twitter Reviews Dataset
 - Validation datasets: Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset, Emotion Dataset for NLP, SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

BETO

#1 Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

Results

#2 Emotion Dataset for NLP

Emotion Dataset for NLP

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

Results

#3 SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

Twitter Reviews Dataset

Results

#4 Twitter Reviews Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

BERT Multilingual

#1 Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

#2 Emotion Dataset for NLP

Emotion Dataset for NLP

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

#3 SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

Twitter Reviews Dataset

#4 Twitter Reviews Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

SVC

#1 Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

#2 Emotion Dataset for NLP

Emotion Dataset for NLP

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

#3 SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

Twitter Reviews Dataset

#4 Twitter Reviews Dataset

Twitter Reviews Dataset

Covid19 Twitter Monitor Dataset

Emotion Dataset for NLP

SMILE Twitter Emotion Dataset

